

IT FAMILY- A NEW NAME FOR EMPLOYEE WELFARE PROGRAMS IN IT ORGANIZATIONSDr. Pankaj Tiwari^{*1}Vikas Pathak²^{*1, 2}Swami Vivekanand University, Sironja Sagar, M.P. 470228**ABSTRACT**

This paper provides an insight towards Employee Welfare programs to be conducted at Organizations workplace. These welfare programs are renamed as IT Family. This is an essential part now as working in IT organizations has become stressful due to excess availability of manpower and high competition. IT Family ensures firm manpower planning and activities to cope up with stress in daily environment of IT working.

Keywords:

LCU (Life Change Units), EWP (Employee Welfare Programs)

INTRODUCTION

Employee welfare Programs in IT organizations to be renamed as **IT Family**. The welfare activities mentioned above must be shadowed under IT Family umbrella. "IT Family" word gives a feeling of acquirement in human brain. People think themselves close to family and actually it's an IT family because an average time is spent by an employee working in organizations. There is less conflict seen in families compared to others. We see many process as well as cultures followed from west in IT organizations the reason for same is we work in close coordination with western counterparts. Its ok we follow, but we cannot ignore cultural values of our nation also. Like Movie theaters follow national anthem as an essential fundamental duties of a civic citizen. **IT Family** Activities must gather National Anthem as a routine exercise per day at a specific time in IT organizations. Generally this part of activity will accelerate employee dedication towards nation and here starts a change to achieve IT Vision 2030. Org. Structure of IT family to be formed by elections among interested employees, this activity will ensure cheerfulness in organizations but also it will ensure there will be no wrong impact on organizations due to such events. IT Family initiatives will also ensure employee Pension prosperity, life insurance schemes and much more which will safeguard mankind and real interests of employees. Under the IT family Initiatives constitutional study will be made mandatory as its highly needed based on current culture followed in organizations. Other nations are very much sensitive in all these areas, so why not our national citizens. IT family initiatives will also ensure social security of employee and other activities like Yoga, meditation and indoor games

IT VISION-2030: These talks about Future Technologies like, Artificial Intelligence, Pocket Supercomputers, Self-Driving Cars, Clean Energy, Virtual and Augmented Reality, Drones and Flying Cars, Crypto currencies, High-Quality Online Education. IT Vision- 2030 approach to make things perfect by year 2030 and helping out our nation to improve its ranking from developing to develop one. A need of IT vision -2030 is most essential for every organization and its employees to follow and are requested to follow Modern Management Techniques in their everyday working.

WELLNESS - THE CONCEPT DELINEATION:

EWPs it first essential to understand the concept of wellness. After the study of a number of definitions of wellness, the researcher feels that the following are most appropriate to mention.

- [1] "Wellness is a lifelong, interactive process of becoming aware of choices and making decisions, creating balanced fulfilling and successful life." Brahma Kumaris, Raj yoga Centre.
- [2] "The concept of total wellness recognizes that our every thought, word, and behavior affects our greater health and well-being. And we, in turn, are affected not only emotionally but also physically and spiritually." Greg Anderson - American best-selling Author and founder of the American Wellness Project
- [3] Dunn defined wellness as – "An integrated method of functioning which is oriented towards maximizing the potential of which the individual is capable. It requires that the individual maintain a continuum of balance and purposeful direction within the environment where he is functioning."

Wellness is being used in the context of alternative medicine since Halbert L. Dunn M.D. began high level wellness in the 1950. "Halbert L. Dunn M.D. began using the phrase high level wellness in the 1950s, based on a series of lectures at a Unitarian Universalist Church in Arlington, Virginia, in the United States".

MEANING OF EMPLOYEE WELLNESS PROGRAMS

The concept Employee Wellness (EW) is the broader concept of Employee Welfare and most of the contemporary organizations have started providing Employee Wellness programs (EWPs). The term Employee Wellness is mostly popular in MNCs in India, and this concept has a great potential towards the organization's growth.

After study of a number of definitions of EWP by the researcher, some of the Definitions of EWPs which were found relevant and appropriate are as mentioned below:

- [1] Programs, such as on-site or subsidized fitness centers, health screenings, smoking cessation, weight reduction/management, health awareness and education, that target keeping employees healthy, thereby lowering employer's costs associated with absenteeism, lost productivity and increased health insurance claims
- [2] A wellness program can include wellness benefits such as fitness training, company sponsored athletics and sports teams, health education, and life improvement classes. It also includes prevention of mental health problems by stress management.
- [3] Employee Wellness Programs are essential to the long-term viability of all businesses. Employee Wellness Programs have been proven to reduce health care costs, absenteeism and presenteeism thus resulting in improved productivity. Research has also shown that Employee Wellness Programs offer a positive Return-on-Investment making them a benefit that costs more to avoid than to Provide.
- [4] The **workplace wellness** program is offered by some employers as a combination of educational, organizational, and environmental activities designed to support behavior conducive to the health of employees in a business and their families. It consists of health education, screening, and interventions designed to change employees' behavior in order to achieve better health and reduce the associated health risks. EWPs are formally introduced in many of the companies and results of those programs are helping organization to reduce absenteeism and increase productivity. Historically, employee health has fallen under the health and safety banner and has been restricted to occupational health related interventions for injuries or illnesses acquired at work. Recent initiatives have begun to challenge this relatively restrictive view of employee health, advocating an expansion of health and safety programs to encompass a more holistic approach to wellness. This approach calls for employers to be proactive rather than reactive to employee health issues, focusing on preventive measures to avoid injuries and illnesses, rather than on the strictly rehabilitative measures in place once an event has occurred. This critical shift in thinking has also led employers to expand the concept of employee health beyond conditions acquired at work to any condition which could potentially impact employee performance. This trend incorporates a wider spectrum of promotion interventions outside the traditional health remit, such as work/life balance initiatives, which are believed to contribute to greater employee wellbeing and employee engagement. After study of the above definitions of EWP, the researcher feels that EWP is not just taking care of employees physical health but also to taking care of mental health and work-life balance, occupation health and life improvement.

NEED FOR EMPLOYEE WELLNESS PROGRAM

There are many reasons to start the EWPs at the workplace. After study of literature, the researcher feels that there are several reasons to start EWPs of which the significant factors are as discussed below:

STRESS AT WORK - THE MOST IMPORTANT FACTOR

The stress is existent in reality; there are many personal and profession reason for it. The stress is good and sometime bad. The stress can be defined as below: "An individual's adaptive response to a situation that is perceived as challenging or threatening to the person's well-being". "No one dies from working too hard. But when people don't get any recognition in their work, the stress of that lack of control can kill them." Barrie S. Grefiff Stress is individual's response to the worrying factor in the environment around him and the consequences of such reaction. Fred Lunthans has rightly defined stress as: "Stress refers to an individual's

response to a disturbing factor in the environment and the consequences of such reaction. Stress is mostly understood to be negative. But it has positive dimension also. Where stress brings out something better from an individual, it is called eustress.

1) Alarm Reaction:

Alarm reaction is an instant reaction for any challenging and fearful situation. The brain causes to send a biochemical message to various parts of the body in these situations which leads to fast breathing, high heart beats, blood pressure, muscle tension and other physiological responses. At Alarm reaction body prepares for resistance stage.

2) Resistance:

At the stage individual's ability to cope up with the environmental demand increases. At this stage body activates behavioral, psychological and biochemical mechanism. This resistance to stress is to some extent. Some people get cold or headache under stress which is explanation for the same.

3) Exhaustion:

People have limited capacity to cope up with stress, if the stress continues for longer period; people will ultimately get in to exhaustion. This general adaptation syndrome process ends before total exhaustion. People who frequently experience the General Adaptation Syndrome have increased risk of long term physiological and psychological damage. General Adaptation syndrome describes stress experience and its only one part of stress, employer and employee should know the reasons and consequences of stress at work. There are many reasons to stress and many causes to Stress. Causes of stress can be divided as per below mentioned diagram and consequences are individual, organizational and burnout.

Organizational Stressors:

Conditions of work and different factors at work can cause stress. It can be divided as per below mentioned diagram as Task Demands, Physical Demands, Role Demands and Interpersonal demands.

Task Demands: These are the stressors related with different task person does at work on the job. The stressors can be divided as Occupation, Security and overload. Some jobs are very stressful by nature. The jobs of teachers, surgeons, BPO employees and Sales Managers have comparatively more stress than their subordinates. Most of the surveys mentioned about the jobs in service sector are very stressful as those jobs are knowledge based. BPO and IT employees have much more stress due to 24 X 7 work culture.

Physical Demands: These are the stressors which are related to physical conditions of work place. It may be temperature or noise at work place. Even sitting arrangement at work place and cleanliness at work place creates stress. Poorly designed offices also provide stress to employees; like private office creates loneliness and too much interaction provides too much disturbance.

Role Demands: These are the stressors related to the role of the employee on the job and behavior expected from the employee on the job. The errors and problems of role on the job create some problems like role ambiguity, role conflict and role overload.

- **Role Ambiguity:** When the person's job is not clear. Person is not very clear about his role on the job or behavior expected on the job.
- **Role Conflict:** It occurs when messages and signals from others about the role are clear but contradictory or mutually exclusive.
- **Role Overload:** Wherein expectation from the role becomes overload which exceeds the person's capacity.

Interpersonal Demands: The last set of organization stressors is interpersonal demands. Most of the jobs are team based jobs and employee has to communicate effectively with the team leaders and team members effectively. If the person has problem with peers or boss for communication that creates stress in the mind. Leadership style may cause stress to the individual and subordinates. Different kind of personalities, culture, perceptions at work create communication barriers which creates stress.

Life Stressors:

Life Changes: there are many changes person goes through like marriage, pregnancy, relationship with spouse, etc. which creates stress. These are many changes in life of person which create impact on organizational settings. Holmes and Rahe reasoned that major changes in a person's life can lead to stress and consequently to disease. Thomas Holmes and Richard Rahe first developed and popularized the notion of life change as a source of stress. Below mentioned table provide details of their findings on major life change events and several of these

events related directly or indirectly to work. The list of events in life may be positive like marriage, vacation or negative like divorce, death of spouse etc. The amount of life stress that a person has experienced in a given period of time, say 1 year is measured by the total number of life change units (LCUs). These units result from the addition of the values (Shown in the right hand column) associated with events that the person has experienced during the target time period. As above, each event's point value supposedly reflects the event's impact on the individual. The extreme event - the death of spouse would be considered as most traumatic event and considered as a point value of 100, On the other hand at minor violation of law rank only 11. These points themselves represent life change units (LCUs). The personal change or change in work place can create stress and which creates health problems in a person.

Life Trauma:

“A Life Trauma is any upheaval in an individual's life that alters his or her attitudes, emotions, or behavior”

Death of the loved one's create turmoil of emotions for few months which affect the health of the person. Major traumas are like marital problems, family difficulties and health problems etc. Millions of Indians experienced traumatic stress on November 26, 2008 Terrorist attacks on Mumbai.

a) Consequences of Stress:

These above all are the kinds of stress person faces. There are many consequences of the stress which can be classified as below

b) Individual Consequences:

These are the outcomes of the stress which mainly affect the individual and organization also suffers directly or indirectly on the same. Stress can produce behavioral, Psychological and medical consequences.

c) Behavioral Consequences:

These are the consequences of stress which may harm the person under stress or others. Person under stress may be more prone to accidents, violence or quarrels. Appetite changes - too much or too little. Eating disorders - anorexia, bulimia. Increased intake of alcohol & other drugs. Increased smoking. Restlessness. Fidgeting. Nail biting. Hypochondria. Workplace aggression.

d) Psychological Consequences:

These are the consequences which affect the person's emotional wellbeing. When the person face too much stress he gets depressed and person experiences low self-esteem.

Difficulties with relations and perception become negative about the closed ones. Stress may also leads to sexual difficulties. Impatience, Fits of rage, Tearfulness, Deterioration of personal hygiene and appearance.

e) Medical Consequences:

These are the consequences which directly affect the individual's physical well-being.

Those consequences are many and some of them are as below:

- Cardiovascular disease
- Immune system disease
- Asthma
- Diabetes
- Digestive disorders
- Ulcers
- Skin complaints - psoriasis
- Headaches and migraines
- Pre-menstrual syndrome
- Depression
- Fatigue
- Loss of sexual drive
- Headaches
- Aches and pains
- Infections
- Indigestion
- Sweating & trembling
- Tingling hands & feet
- Breathlessness
- Missed heartbeats

- Ulcers

f) Organizational Consequences:

If the person is experiencing stress, he faces individual consequences and those consequences directly or indirectly create impact on the organization. The consequences on the organization are as below:

- 1) **Performance:** Too much stress decreases the performance of the person. The managers can take faulty decisions or face difficulties to take decision or even disruption in working relationship. The relationship between boss and subordinate or relationship between peers may be spoiled due to stress.
- 2) **Withdrawal:** Withdrawal means just cutting interest in work and achieve target. The people who cannot cope up with stress try to be absent from work. Absenteeism increases and lack of interest in the work are also consequences of stress. Managers start missing deadlines and also cannot achieve their targets.
- 3) **Attitudes:** Change in attitude is obvious when person cannot cope up with the stress. The consequences are like no job satisfaction, low morale and organizational commitment can suffer. As a result people may tend to complain about unimportant things at work.
- 4) **Burnout:** The process of emotional exhaustion, cynicism and reduced efficacy (Lower Feeling of personal accomplishment) resulting from prolonged exposure to stress. Burnout is because of excessive demands made on people who serve or frequently interact with others. Burn out is normally due to interpersonal or role related stressors.

THE WORKFORCE IS CHARACTERIZED AS CAPTIVE:

Usually employees are at work 5 days a week and this large group is actually caged due to the nature of the workday and 24x7 work culture in IT and ITeS Companies.

WORKPLACE - GOOD PLACE TO ADDRESS THE HEALTH ISSUES SOCIALLY:

Repeated exposure to health education and communication can create awareness of importance of health at workplace and which can be discussed in between the employees.

EMPLOYEE WORK-LIFE BALANCE:

Work – Life Scenario: Work-life Balance is balancing act of Work life and personal life. Many researchers mentioned via survey that more than 60 % of the respondents, professionals surveyed revealed that they are not able to balance work life and personal life demands. “Work-Life balance is about creating supportive, healthy, work environments for employees who are striving to better integrate their work and personal responsibilities

Work-life balance is a broad concept including proper prioritizing between career and ambition on one hand, compared with pleasure, leisure, family and spiritual development on the other. A range of practices designed to improve the balance between the demands of an Employee’s work and personal life. As we are aware most the workforce in this era is Generation X and Generation Y and which is very modern. The competition and globalization has demand of challenging jobs. We can see below, how jobs have become more challenging and one particular person has to keep a balance of so many activities. Increasing number of work hours or target oriented jobs are also reasons which are making persons workaholic that leads to imbalance between personal life and work – life. Work-life balance is an issue for many of the professionals who are working in BPO sector, IT professionals, doctors and nurses. This is an important concern for the employer and employees both. Employers are losing lots of profits due to problems of work-life balance of employees as it directly leads to absenteeism.

Companies are striving to help employees for their work-life balance by providing the following facilities:

- Spread out hours.
- Flexi-time.
- Time Management Training.
- Stress management Training.
- Work from home.
- Compressed work hours.
- Job sharing.
- Shift swapping.
- Job rotation.

There are many benefits work- life balance to employer and employees. This is enlisted as below:

- Well-being of employees and good health.

- Reduced absenteeism.
- Reduces stress related problems.
- Employee loyalty and high employee morale.
- Improved employer brand.
- Better employee relations.
- Reduced use of sick leave.
- Lower recruitment and training cost.

Role of IT Organizations: Some of the factor which is very much appreciated by employees in organizations in current scenarios is like:

- Safety for employees, transport facility in case of late working.
- Employee welfare programs to relieve stress.
- Good opportunity to average associates and helping them to enjoy a civilized life by getting good remuneration and chance of quality work in knowledge industry. Good remuneration compared to traditional industries.
- Due to IT centers located in various parts of nation it helps directly and indirectly to many people like Government to Generate revenue, employees, vendors, cab taxi/ rental services, real estate market, food processing industry, cloth industry, nearby tourist earning, technological institutions to get hand's on over real technological drivers etc. thing.
- A desire of strong education among people so as to enter into knowledge industry.
- Hygienic working atmosphere and safe drinking water.
- Flexibility to work based on acquired technical skills, multiple chance of getting similar work based on good hands on experience.
- Opportunity to work at onsite locations and based on acquired skills by the employee.
- Best suited industry for women, organizations provide great help to female employees like work from home, leave benefits, doctor facility, transportation benefits etc.
- Financial benefit from banks, financial institutions for corporate employees at lower interest rates.
- Higher education assistance programs, leave without pay to employees while doing education is an appreciable policy by organizations.
- LTC benefit, medical benefit, employee provident fund and housing are the others taken into consideration.

Innovative HR practices:

- [1] **EMPLOYEE ACQUISITION STRATEGIES** (e.g. greater importance to Be attached to fit between person and company culture, emphasizing 'career' not 'job' and selling company image to attract potential employees, referral bonuses, sign on bonuses for new employees, psychological testing, developing industry academia interface, etc.)
- [2] **EMPLOYEE RETENTION STRATEGIES** (e.g. evolving a pleasant work environment, deferred compensation, competitive salaries, faster promotions, greater work autonomy, etc.)
- [3] **COMPENSATION and INCENTIVES** (e.g. increasing component of variable pay, stock options, combining individual and team incentives, performance-linked incentives, customization of perks to individual needs, offering a variety of allowances, conducting compensation surveys, etc.)
- [4] **BENEFITS and SERVICES** (e.g. focus on long-term benefits for employees through alternative insurance and health management schemes, giving benefits directed at employees' families, flexible employee benefits /cafeteria approach, child and elder care programs, improvements in retirement benefits)
- [5] **REWARDS and RECOGNITION** (e.g. performance-linked rewards, flexible rewards, cash rewards for extraordinary performance, rewarding team performance, best employee awards, public recognition of good performance at a company meeting or function, recognition from coworkers, Blend of financial and non-financial rewards)
- [6] **TECHNICAL TRAINING** (e.g. systematic training needs assessment, cross functional training, providing job relevant training, facilitating transfer of training to actual job performance, etc.)
- [7] **MANAGEMENT DEVELOPMENT (MD)** (e.g. linking MD to individual needs, linking MD to organizational objectives, using innovative MD methods, like stress management programs, adventure training, leadership and attitudinal training, study leave, programs for women managers, etc.)

- [8] **CAREER PLANNING and DEVELOPMENT PRACTICES** (e.g. developing career paths, providing fast-track career plans, providing mentors to employees, cross-functional career paths, participative career plans, career counseling, etc.)
- [9] **PERFORMANCE APPRAISALS** (e.g. giving weight to individual, team and organizational performance while appraising; using quantifiable criteria for appraisals; participative appraisals; open appraisals to increase transparency; giving appraisal feedback; linking rewards to appraisals, 360 appraisals, etc.)
- [10] **POTENTIAL DEVELOPMENT:** a company-wide MD program (job rotations, use of assessment centers, coaching, conducting potential appraisals, etc.)
- [11] **SUCCESSION PLANNING:** MDprogram aimed at filling specific position with one of the two potential candidates (e.g. identifying replacements, provision of fall-back positions in case of failure, preparing to assume higher responsibility, etc.)
- [12] **EMPLOYEE RELATIONS WITH A HUMAN FACE: TREATINGEMPLOYEES WITH CONCERN** (e.g. information sharing, open and transparent communication, family get-togethers, humanizing work environment, respecting employees, ensuring fairness in management practices, encouraging risk-taking, etc.)
- [13] **EMPLOYEE EXIT and SEPARATION MANAGEMENT** (e.g. extending benefits to retirees for lifetime, retirement planning workshops for about-to retireemployees, conducting exit interviews, Out placement services, VRS, etc.)
- [14] **ADOPTING RESPONSIBILITY FOR SOCIALLY RELEVANT ISSUES** (e.g. adult education programs, community development projects, concern for greening and environment protection, research promotion, etc.)

Previous Research and Review of Literature on Stress:

Louise Tourigny, Vishwanath V. Cake and Xiaoyun Wang (2010) incontestable that role overload and role conflict have vital positive effects on job stress. Moreover, each shift work and its interference with non-work activities considerably elevated the impact of role overload on job stress. Findings conjointly reveal that call latitude lessened the pre judicious impact of role overload on job stress for workers engaged on mounted shift, however not for workers engaged on rotating shift. Chet E. Barney and Steven m. Elias (2010), in regard to accidental motivation, a major interaction was determined between job stress, flex-time and country of residence. Though flextime and country of residence were vital predictors of intrinsic motivation, no vital interactions were determined.

David Prottas (2008) suggests that self-employment, either as an owner or freelance, is an efficient plan of action for people to extend their job autonomy. However, there was no proof that the freelance take issue from staff with relation to the profit they receive from the work autonomy they understand.

George Halkos and Dimitrios Bousinakis (2010) found that redoubled stress ends up in reduced productivity and redoubled satisfaction ends up in redoubled productivity. Once work begins to overlap with workers personal life this suggests a negative impact on productivity. Quality work is a lot of associated with conscientiousness and private satisfaction than work load. Energetic and active people have an effect on productivity absolutely. To boot, within the study, the states of stress and job satisfaction square measure the results of the interaction of the environment s demands with the private characteristics.

Mohd Dahlan A. Malek, Kathryn Mearns and Rhona Flin (2010) found that the sources of activity stress have vital negative correlations with job satisfaction and psychological wellbeing. The results of the multivariate analysis indicate that overall header behavior incorporates a vital influence on overall job satisfaction for United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland hearth fighters however not for Malaysian hearth fighters. However, overall header behavior incorporates a vital impact as a moderating variable between sources of stress and psychological health for Malaysian hearth fighters.

Colette Darcy and Alma Mccarthy (2007), the analysis findings offer initial support for the chance that the factors influencing work-family conflict take issue for every of the parenting teams analyzed. For all oldsters with dependent kids it absolutely was found that job involvement, job stress and colleague support all have prognosticative powers in terms of explaining the antecedents of work-family conflict.

Linda Lee Larson (2004) indicated that the structure job stressors in work surroundings were a lot of a supply of stress than the supposed individual job factors.

Peter Callender (1989) prompt try kinds of problems directly: team building, management action teams and one to one development counsel.

Jagdish K. Dua (1994) indicated that employees used at the upper job levels square measure less stressed than those used at the lower job levels and support employees. Each the work stress and non-work stress square measure related to poor physical health, poor emotional health and high job discontent.

Factors Affecting Employee Wellness Program due to Globalization:

- Work Pressure due to project Deliverables
- Virtual Teams
- Cross Cultural Sensitivities
- Growth of MNCs in India
- Working Hours Across the Globe
- Competition among Organizations
- Insecurity due to seniority in an organization
- Pressure working atmosphere
- Non Fitment due to different work allotment
- Employee Desire of high remuneration
- Manager's Behavior
- Organizational culture
- Long working hours
- Target Oriented Job
- Family responsibilities
- Fast Life Style
- Night Shift
- Competition
- Ineffective Time Management
- Insecurity of losing Job
- Qualified employees have the opportunity to be promoted to positions of greater pay and/or responsibility within the organization.
- Employees are interested in following shortcut techniques.
- Lack of long term vision in employees.

The wellness is generally used to convey the healthy status of body, mind and spirit which provide feeling of overall wellbeing.

PHYSICAL WELLNESS:

“It is health that is real wealth and not pieces of gold and silver.”- *Mahatma Gandhi*

As Physical wealth has more importance than Gold and Silver. Physical Wellness is a wellness of body of the human being with no disease. The body of a person is mostly the outcome of the hereditary characteristics. The healthy body without disease provides positive energy to mind and which also helps for psychological wellness. Physical Wellness is characterized by following fact: Good physical health – free from disease and energetic and dynamic.

a) Physical Illness:

Cardio-vascular ailment – High blood pressure, heart disease. Immune related disorder – Asthma, Allergy, Skin problems. Ulcers and digestive disorder etc. Diabetes. Obesity. Chronic pain. Feminine health problems etc.

b) Physical Wellness can be achieved by following measures:

Physical exercise. Yoga. Walking / hiking. Aerobics. Dance. Eating nutritious food.

PSYCHOLOGICAL WELLNESS/EMOTIONAL WELLNESS:

Individual's status of mind is an important aspect of this wellness process. This wellness is also called as "Emotional Wellness". Following aspects are involved:

Expression of Emotions. Coping up with stress, failures and success. Adapting to a new environment, culture and people. As per Chinese Proverb, "Where mind goes, the body follows." Status of mind effects on the body of the individual and may lead to physical health problem. Individual attitude is the imperative factor of thinking process. Attitude can create positive thoughts and negative thoughts.

a) Psychological Illness:

Low Self Esteem. Stress. Depression / Hypertension. Lack of interest. Loneliness. Insecurity. Helplessness. Anxiety. Depression. Eating disorders, and Substance abuse.

b) Psychological Wellness Measures:

It can be achieved by following measures: Yoga. Meditation. Mentoring. Counseling. Advice from parents and Gurus.

SPIRITUAL WELLNESS:

"Wisdom is to the soul what health is to the body" - *De Saint-Real quotes*

Spiritual wellness is understanding the real "self" and meaning of life. Spirituality is to find out the meaning of following questions like. Who I am? What is the purpose of life? How I can be in shape with the world? It is also linked with the having understanding about others and also appreciating beauty outside own self.

Spirituality is result of ethics, values, culture, relation and beliefs etc.

a) Spiritual Illness:

Unable to still the mind. Over-sensitive to criticism. Orientation to the past. Lack of concentration, Lack of creativity. Mental confusion. Difficulty in making decisions etc.

b) Spiritual Wellness Measures:

Following measures can help spiritual wellness:

Meditation. Self – talk. Reading religious / self-help books. Advice from Gurus / Saints.

SOCIAL WELLNESS:

"Our greatest joy-and our greatest pain comes in our relationships with others" - Stephen R. Covey As per the above quote, relationship personal or social matters a lot. Social health is very crucial part of life of human being. Human being is a Social Animal. Social wellness means enriching life through education and work for the benefit and satisfaction of self and others in your community. Social wellness creates a positive impact on others and relationships with others around you are healthy.

a) Characteristics of Social wellness:

Harmonious relationship with family and community. Existence in society. Impact on people around individual.

b) Social illness: Signs of social illness are:

Problem with relationship. Avoidance. Fast speech. Panic. Nervous laughter.

c) Measures for Social Wellness:

Communication skills Training. Networking skills. Understanding others. Reading Books. Interacting with people.

INTELLECTUAL WELLNESS:

Intellectual wellness is learning new things and thinking in a different perspective. It is being active with maximum intellectual activities in life. Understanding importance of different things in life and giving priorities intellectually.

a) Characteristics Intellectual Wellness:

Learning continuously. Good listener. Trying new things. Good Communication. Thinking.

b) Measures for Intellectual:

Reading - Pick up a newspaper or educational pamphlet. By choosing to read, you not only increase your intellect, you remain knowledgeable about current misuses and past events.

Try to learn something new every day: Keep your eyes and mind open to new ideas and focus on learning something new each day. Challenge yourself to see more than one side of an issue. Watch educational television and enlighten your mind. Learn to appreciate art: Attend exhibits, plays, musicals, and poetry readings. Attend an educational workshop or seminar, not because you are earning credit, but because you want to increase your knowledge.

ENVIRONMENTAL WELLNESS:

It is being happy with the personal and professional environmental individual lives in. Environmental issues can create impact on physical and psychological wellness of individual.

a) Environmental Factors affecting on wellness:

Water. Natural Calamities. Food. Work place hygiene. Work place settings.

b) Measures of Environmental Wellness:

Taking care of work environment. Understanding environment of the outside world and adjusting with the same Ergonomics.

OCCUPATIONAL WELLNESS:

This wellness is job-related or work-related. It depends on the satisfaction of the individual person on the job in relation with the work, pay, and other factors related to work.

Occupational Wellness can be achieved by:

Choosing correct career which is liked by the individual or may be the individual is passionate about the same. Continuous improvement and value addition in the job related competencies which are helpful to the organization and individual both.

FINANCIAL WELLNESS:

Most of the Individuals are worried about their economic status. The financial status of individual directly contributes to the stress of individual. Stress is created due to debt or credits, compensation packages, etc. On the contrary the financially secured employee is more engaged at work and less stressed at job.

Financial Wellness can be achieved by: Proper knowledge of financial planning and implementing the financial planning rules in daily life.

CONCLUSION

Due to Managerial Mismanagement at workplace it's become essential now days to strengthen IT family initiatives. Organizations must follow IT family initiatives and there is a strong need of forming IT regulations. IT family initiatives are gaining popularity now a days as awareness is increasing amongst IT associates. A firm coordination as well as genuine positive approach is required to achieve IT-Vision 2030 is in demand and every body must ensure their participation in achieving the same.

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